

IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF SOLAR PANEL

Shinde Mayur Balasaheb,
Department of Mechanical Engineering, S.B.Patil college of engineering Indapur,
City:Indapur Dis: Pune Contry:India
E-mail:12mayurshinde@gmail.com

Shaikh Mohamadsaied Rubab
Department of Mechanical Engineering, S.B.Patil college of engineering Indapur,
City:Indapur Dis:Pune Contry:India
E-mail:mohamadsaied81@gmail.com

Mulani Saifali Abbas
Department of Mechanical Engineering, S.B.Patil college of engineering Indapur,
City:Indapur Dis:Pune Contry:India
E-mail:saifalimulani1@gmail.com

Abstract— An operating temperature is governing parameter of solar panel. As temperature of solar panel is increased then efficiency of solar panel decreases. The different solar panels stations do not work effectively once the temperature exceeds 45°C. In our project we are looking forward to optimize their efficiency in absorbing sun radiations. The methodology that will be used is using water for cooling them down, to increase the temperature inside the panel and therefore to work at its maximum efficiency. The challenge in this project is to solve the problem with minimum water used to cool down panel.

Keywords- Solar Panel, Arduino microcontroller, LM35 Sensor .

1 Introduction

As the world is facing the problem of energy deficit, global warming and deterioration of environment and energy sources, there is need for an alternative energy resource for power generation other than use of fossil fuels, water and wind. Fossil fuel get depleted in next few decades, hydro power plants are depends on annual rainfall and wind power is also depends on climate changes. Solar energy is one of the comparable candidate for alternate energy source. But temperature is main parameter in this , As temperature of solar panel is increased then efficiency of solar panel decreases. The different solar panels stations do not work effectively once the temperature exceeds 45°C.

A typical PV module has an ideal conversion efficiency in the range of 15%. The remaining energy is converted into heat and this heat increases the operating temperature of PV system which affects the electrical power production of PV modules and this can also cause the structural damage of PV modules leads to shorting its life span and lowering conversion efficiency.

The temperature increase of 1K corresponds to the reduction of the photoelectric conversion efficiency by 0.2%-0.5%. Various studies have been conducted in order to improve the PV conversion efficiency, among these cooling provides a good solution for the low efficiency problem. Both water and air are suitable as the cooling

fluid to cool the PV module in order to avoid the drop of electrical efficiency.

1.1 Problem Statement

Photovoltaic solar cell generates electricity by receiving solar irradiance. The electrical efficiency of photovoltaic (PV) cell is adversely affected by the significant increase of cell operating temperature during absorption of solar radiation. This undesirable effect can be partially avoided by fixing a water absorption sponge on the back side of the photovoltaic panel and maintain wet condition by circulation of drop by drop water through sponge.

As temperature of solar panel is increased then efficiency of solar panel decreases. Ideal conversion efficiency is in the range of 15%. The remaining energy is converted into heat and this heat increases the operating temperature of PV system which affects the electrical power production of PV modules and this can also cause the structural damage of PV modules leads to shorting its life span and lowering conversion efficiency.

1.2 Objective

The objective of the present work is to reduce the temperature of the solar cell in order to increase its electrical conversion efficiency.

Get the temperature reading directly on LCD screen and automatic cooling will start.

1.3 Scope of work

Solar panel system is very common in each part of contry. It is used in many big renewable energy projects and has huge benefits in power supplying. However the main problematic is the efficiency of this system. Main problem of reducing efficiency is solved by water cooling method. This has high scope in hot areras and also due to use of renewable energy.

2 Materials and Methods

1. Solar Panel = 20watt, 18 volt
2. Small submersible water pump
3. Tube
4. Arduino microcontroller
5. LM35 Sensor
6. LCD

At standard temperature (25°C)

$$\alpha_i = 0.045\%/^{\circ}\text{K}$$

$$\alpha_v = -0.34\%/^{\circ}\text{K}$$

α_i = Temperature coe. Of I_{max}

α_v = Temperature coe. Of V_{max}

$$\alpha_i = ((\text{Change in } I / I_{@std.}) \times 100) / (\Delta T)$$

$$\alpha_v = ((\text{Change in } V / V_{@std.}) \times 100) / (\Delta T)$$

Percentage of increase in current is lesser than percentage of decrease in voltage.

Therefore output power decreases and efficiency decreases.

Conclusion

As the temperature increases voltage of panel is decreases with higher rate and that of current of panel increases with smaller rate.

It is need to maintain temperature of solar panel below particular value because the temperature above 25c affects the performance and efficiency.

Reference

- 1) V.Jafari fesharaki Majid Dehghani, J.Jafari Fesharaki, Humed Tarasoli, "The effect of tempratue of photovoltaic cell efficiency",first international conference on emerging trend in energy conservation- ETEC Tehran ,Tehran,Iran.
- 2) Anna Machniewics, Dominika knera, Dariusz Heim, "Effect of transition temprature on efficiency of PV/PCM", Sixth international building physics conference IBPC 2015 energy procedia 78(2015)1684-1689.
- 3) K.A. Moharram M.S. Abd -Elhaldy, H.a. Kandil, H. El-Sherif, "Enhancing the performance of PV PANELS by water cooling", Ain Shams Engineering Journal(2013)4,869-877.
- 4) Catain George Popovici, Sebastian Veleriu Hudisteanu, Theodor Dorin Mateescu, Nelucristian Chereches, "Efficiency improvement of photovoltaic panels by usimg air cooled heat simks", sustainable solution for enrgy and enviroment, EENVIR_YRC 2015, Bucharest, Romana, energy procedia 85(2016)425-432.
- 5) B.Koteswararao, K. Radha krishna, P.Vijay, N.Raja surya, "Experimental Analysis of solar panel efficiency with different modes of cooling", e-ISSN : 0975-4024 B.Koteswararao et al. / International Journal of Engineering and Technology (IJET).
- 6) Yogesh S Bijjargi, Kale S.S and Shaikh K.A, "Cooling techniques for photovoltaic module for improving its conversion efficiency: a review", International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology (IJMET) Volume 7, Issue 4, July-Aug 2016, pp.22-28, Article ID: IJMET_07_04_003.